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5 3 **Title: The ecological footprint of dwelling construction in Spain**
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18
19 8 **Abstract**

20 9 The construction industry is well known for its high impact on the environment; an even
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22 10 higher impact has taken place in recent years due to the real-estate bubble which has
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24 11 resulted in a surplus in the construction of dwellings in many countries. In Spain, about
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26 12 500,000 dwellings were constructed during 2006-2010, which represent a 2% increase
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28 13 in four years. In the present work, a methodology is defined as the first step towards
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30 14 the creation of an effective assessment of the Ecological Footprint of this type of
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32 15 construction. The procedure is based on the project budget and its bill of quantities,
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34 16 organized by means of a systematic construction-work breakdown structure which
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36 17 divides the work into three major categories: materials, manpower, and machinery.
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38 18 Each stream generates partial footprints (i.e. energy, food, mobility, construction
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40 19 materials, and waste).
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45 20 Ninety-two dwelling construction projects, which represent the most commonly built
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47 21 dwellings in Spain per statistical data from the authorities, are evaluated and their
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49 22 Ecological Footprints are determined. The indicator is sensitive to various building
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51 23 typologies, which range from detached houses to multi-family buildings. Detached
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53 24 houses generate an Ecological Footprint per square metre constructed of 1.5 times
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55 25 higher than that of 4-floor multi-family buildings and the indicator remains practically
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57 26 constant for taller buildings. This emphasises that not only is the traditional Spanish
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1 construction of a compact city with multi-storey buildings environmentally better from
2 the mobility standpoint, but also from the building construction standpoint.

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8 **Keywords:** ecological footprint, construction and demolition waste, building
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10 construction, Spain, construction breakdown system

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14 7 **1. Introduction**

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20 9 During the past decade, Spain has experienced a huge construction bubble which has
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22 caused the biggest economic crisis since democracy was introduced (COAAT
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24 Barcelona, 2010). Not only does this high construction rate exert an impact in the
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26 economy, but it also causes an impact on the Spanish environment, which has yet to
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28 be evaluated. This construction is analyzed in Table 1 from official statistical data
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30 generated by the Ministry of Development in Spain (2011). The typical construction
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32 characteristics can be obtained from the same report and are multi-family buildings with
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34 2 or more dwellings, 4 or more floors above ground level and 1 below ground level;
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36 each dwelling has a 72 m² floor space, 2 bathrooms, a garage and is privately owned.
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38 The building structure is of reinforced concrete with unidirectional beams, ceramic roof,
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40 ceramic façade, aluminium carpentry, wooden doors, false ceilings and exterior blinds.
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46 20 The economic impact of this construction is well known, and resulted in an economic
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48 crisis that started in 2008 and continues to the present day. However, little has been
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50 done in order to measure its environmental impact. It is necessary to assess this
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52 through indicators, so that the weight of the environmental impacts can be qualified and
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54 quantified. The tools that analyze these impacts generally follow the methodology of
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56 Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA) (Zabalza Bribián et al., 2011; Malmqvist and Glaumann,
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58 2009). However, other approaches exist, such as the Emergy Analysis (Meillaud et al.,
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1 2005), and the Material Flow Analysis (Sinivuori and Saari, 2006). Currently there is a
2 tendency to use simpler methodologies as they can be more easily understood by
3 society, among which feature the Carbon Footprint (Weidema et al., 2008; Solís-
4 Guzmán et al., 2014) and the Ecological Footprint (EF) (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996).
5 The latter can be adapted to the unique characteristics of the construction sector, and
6 has been chosen for its comprehensibility, transparency, and adaptability (Cagiao et
7 al., 2011).

8 The EF indicator was introduced by Wackernagel and Rees (1996), who measured the
9 EF of humanity and compared it with the carrying capacity of the planet. According to
10 its definition, the EF is the amount of land that would be required to provide the
11 resources (grain, feed, firewood, fish, and urban land) and absorb the emissions (CO₂)
12 of humanity (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996; WWF, 2008). By comparing the EF to the
13 amount of land available, Wackernagel concluded that human consumption of
14 resources currently stands 50% above the global carrying capacity in developed
15 countries (WWF, 2010). The indicator has been used since its inception to determine
16 impacts on greatly differing scales: to predict the impacts generated by humankind on
17 Planet Earth, for the periodic calculation of the footprint of humankind on Planet Earth,
18 and for periodically calculating the EF of different countries, cities, productive sectors,
19 and industries (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013).

20 In this paper, Spanish dwelling construction is studied in 92 different projects by
21 applying the procedure developed by Spanish researchers (Domenech Quesada,
22 2007; Cagiao et al., 2011) on corporate EF calculation and on the process of building
23 construction (Solís-Guzmán, 2011; Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013).

24 This research, therefore, aims to bring all previous knowledge related to the EF
25 indicator into the residential building sector in order to analyze the construction phase
26 of dwellings, and to determine the advantages and disadvantages that this indicator

1 may yield in the analysis of environmental impact on the building sector. Among the
2 studies which apply the EF indicator in the construction sector is Bastianoni et al.
3 (2007) who calculate the EF of two Italian buildings by taking into account the
4 embodied energy of construction materials and that of the construction processes: the
5 latter measuring only 5% of the former. The results generate three types of EF: CO₂
6 absorption land, forest land (for production of wooden materials) and the built land
7 occupied directly. Solís-Guzmán et al. (2013) develop a similar model with some
8 innovative hypotheses in that they include the workers food and mobility and the water
9 consumption on the construction site; these factors are not normally included in the EF
10 methodology. Teng and Wu (2014) analyzed the building life cycle (project design,
11 construction, usage and demolition) in terms of EF (energy, resources, CO₂ and solid
12 waste) and applied the methodology to an exposition centre in Wuhan, China.

13 The EF indicator has also been applied in the evaluation of high-rise districts in Tehran
14 (Samadpour and Faryadi, 2008), real-estate development in Nanjing, China (Li et al.,
15 2008), farmhouse construction (Zhao and Mao, 2013), hotel construction (Li and
16 Cheng, 2010) and centenary house rehabilitation (Bin and Parker, 2012). Furthermore,
17 an Ecological and Carbon Footprint evaluation tool has been defined for buildings
18 (Olgyay, 2008).

19 The following procedure for the assessment of the EF in the construction of residential
20 buildings is based on the project bill of quantities and on the systematic classification of
21 construction work (Marrero and Ramirez-de-Arellano, 2010): materials, manpower, and
22 machinery. An approach to the calculation of the EF, valid for any residential building
23 construction, is described in detail therein.

24 For the selection of projects, the following steps were taken:

- 25 1. Search for current projects which represent the most common typologies.

1 2. Create a resource quantification database by means of a construction breakdown
2 system (CBS), which defines materials, machinery, and manpower.

3 3. Once all project data is processed, the EF is calculated, based mainly on the
4 authors' previously established methodology (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013) and on new
5 approaches to the quantification of resources, to the energy consumption of machinery,
6 and to water consumption during the construction work.

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8 The modifications to Solís-Guzmán et al. (2013) model are:

- 9 1. A separate analysis of construction and demolition waste from urban solid waste.
- 10 2. Determination of materials EF from a newly created resource quantification
11 database.
- 12 3. Definition of machinery EF directly from the gasoline or diesel consumption.
- 13 4. Definition of the water EF from the actual consumption in 90 different construction
14 projects.
- 15 5. A calculation strategy which allows, with a straight forward methodology, to adapt a
16 CBS to the EF indicator.

17 18 **2. Methodology**

19 The present analysis of the EF focuses on the implementation and construction phase
20 of residential buildings: research into the other two phases of the life cycle of buildings,
21 those of use and demolition, does not constitute part of the present analysis. A second
22 assumption is also considered: the only activity that exerts an impact on the study area
23 is that which corresponds to the construction of the residential buildings considered
24 above. The project budget becomes the main source of information for the

1 quantification of the resources consumed during the building construction. The
2 construction industry normally organizes works clearly in the project budget since cost
3 control is always a major issue. The budgets of 92 different dwelling projects, which
4 met the construction characteristics evaluated in the previous section, are analyzed
5 and classified; their budgets are reorganized in a CBS which enables comparison. This
6 system, for the organization of the work and its quantities, has been successfully
7 applied to control the generation of construction waste (Solís-Guzmán et al. 2009) and
8 project cost (Marrero et al. 2014). In Table 2, the measurement of the projects is
9 presented in terms of the average quantities per square metre constructed. These are
10 grouped per number of floors above ground level. The sample sizes are: 4 projects with
11 one floor, 2 with two floors, 22 with three floors, 22 with four floors, 20 with five floors,
12 and 22 with ten floors.

13
14 Once the quantities per project characteristic are defined, the next step is to translate
15 them into specific consumed resources, which is possible by means of the CBS
16 employed. Each Q_i listed in Table 2 is transformed into three types of resources:
17 manpower, materials, and machinery. The systematic classification of the Andalusia
18 Construction Cost Database (ACCD, 2010) is used. The ACCD structure is
19 hierarchical, with clearly defined levels, whereby each group is divided into subgroups
20 of similar characteristics (Marrero and Ramirez-de-Arellano, 2010). As an example, in
21 Table 3, the quantity Q_i 05F “Concrete and ceramic slab” is shown and its
22 corresponding resources are listed and grouped into: materials, manpower, and
23 machinery. Five different unitary costs, obtained from the ACCD, are used to define the
24 average quantity of each item which forms part of the unitary cost. The same
25 procedure is carried out for each of the classification elements in Table 2: 02T, 02R,
26 02P, etc. The final result is established as a resource quantification database (RQDB)

1 which enables the evaluation of all typical Spanish dwelling constructions from the
2 point of view of consumed resources.

3 The RQDB (manpower, construction materials, and machinery resources), defined
4 previously, are not the only resources consumed during building construction. Three
5 additional resources: electricity, water, and built land, and the waste generation also
6 generate an EF and are defined from the general project characteristics, such as
7 surface constructed, project total cost, and type of construction, see Fig. 1 second
8 level. The new model improvements with respect to Solís-Guzmán et al. (2013) are in
9 the EF calculation of waste, materials, machinery and water, as explained in the
10 introduction.

11 Manpower is the first resource defined from the project budget data and the RQDB
12 created. In building construction, the operators consume food and fuel in their
13 transportation back and forth from the construction site, and they also generate
14 municipal solid waste (MSW) during their working hours. These impacts are identified
15 in the third level of Fig.1. The second resource is the building material, which, through
16 manufacturing processes, transportation and installation (see Fig.1), consumes energy
17 from different sources (necessary for the material extraction, manufacture and
18 commissioning) and fuel (during transportation of the material from the factory to the
19 construction site). The third and last resource is the machinery and tools used in the
20 construction work. The machinery can be grouped into two families depending on its
21 engine: combustion or electric, however, only combustion engines are considered in
22 this resource. The electricity consumed is considered a separate resource, because it
23 is not only consumed by electric machines but also by the construction site lighting, air
24 conditioning, heating and domestic hot water. All these aspects depend on the general
25 characteristics of the project. The same occurs with the water consumption on site. The
26 next resource considered is the plot where the construction itself is built, which
27 consumes land, and consequently has a footprint. Finally, the building construction

1 generates waste, normally referred to as construction and demolition waste (CDW) and
2 is considered a separate impact.

3 Partial and total footprints, generated in the construction phase of the dwelling sector,
4 are defined by means of the intermediate elements and their corresponding
5 coefficients. These are located in the bottom level of Fig.1, and are represented by
6 green boxes: pasture, cropland, productive sea, energy, forest, built land, and total
7 ecological footprint.

8 For these calculations, up-to-date equivalence factors (e) must be considered for the
9 project, in order to transform the results expressed into global hectares over hectares
10 (gha). These equivalence factors are shown in Table 4.

11 **2.1. Determination of the EF of manpower: food consumption**

12 The initial assumption of this section is that workers' food is attributed to the EF of the
13 building construction since this activity takes place on the worksite, in the same way as
14 in the methodology developed by Domenech Quesada (2007), where business meals
15 are allocated to the Corporate Ecological Footprint. To this end, the total number of
16 manpower hours worked for the entire construction project must first be calculated and
17 is obtained from the RQDB.

18 The footprint is calculated using the expression:

$$19 \quad EF_{wfd} = \frac{EF_m \cdot N_w \cdot N_{wd}}{h_m \cdot h_w} \quad (1)$$

20 where

21 EF_{wfd} : Weighted ecological footprint of food (gha/year)

22 EF_m : Ecological footprint expressed as gha/year/meal

23 N_w : Number of workers on the construction site

1 N_{wd} : Number of working days

2 h_m : 8 hours/meal. One meal per working day is assumed

3 h_w : Working hours per day (8 working hours per day).

4 The EF_m values per food type for a typical menu are calculated by Solís-Guzmán et al.
5 (2013), and are summarized in Table 5.

6 **2.2. Determination of the manpower EF: mobility**

7 The fuel consumption is obtained in units of volume (litres), and the footprint of fuel
8 consumption can be expressed as:

$$9 \quad EF_{wf} = \frac{F}{EP} \cdot e_f \quad (2)$$

10 where

11 EF_{wf} : Weighted ecological footprint of fuel consumption (gha/year)

12 F : Fuel consumption (GJ). The energy intensity of the fuel is 35 MJ/l (Domenech
13 Quesada, 2007).

14 e_f : equivalence factor of forests (gha/ha)

15 EP : Energy productivity of fuel, which is considered as oil (Table 6). Energy
16 productivity of fuel is expressed as:

$$17 \quad EP = \frac{A}{E} \quad (3)$$

18 where A is the absorption factor and E is the emission factor. The absorption factor is
19 taken as $A = 5.21$ tonnes of CO_2 /ha per year (Domenech Quesada, 2007). The
20 emission factor of oil is in Table 6 together with other energy sources for use in later
21 sections.

1 **2.3. Determination of manpower EF: municipal solid waste**

2 The determination of the EF of municipal solid waste (MSW) is based on statistical data
3 and on the energy intensity of the materials (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013), now simplified
4 and summarized in Table 7. The coefficients (CR_x) are defined as organic, paper,
5 plastic, and glass waste, and are measured in tonnes (G_x) generated per worker.

6 The total generation of MSW in tonnes of each waste stream “i”, G_i, is obtained by
7 multiplying the aforementioned statistical data, G_x, by the number of workers on the
8 construction site. Finally, the following expression is used for the determination of the
9 total footprint of the waste,

10
$$EF_{wms} = \sum_i CR_{x_i} \cdot G_i (4),$$

11 where:

12 EF_{wms}: Weighted EF of the waste (gha/year)

13 CR_{xi}: Weighted Conversion Rate (gha/year/t)

14 G_i: Waste Generation (t)

15 **2.4. Determination of the EF of construction materials**

16 The footprint of construction materials is determined using the following expression:

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18
$$EF_{wm} = \frac{\sum_i Cm_i \cdot Ese_{mi}}{EP} \cdot e_f (5)$$

19 where:

20 EF_{wm}: Weighted EF of construction materials (gha/year)

21 Cm_i: Material consumption (kg)

1 E_{se_{mi}}: Specific embodied energy of material i (MJ/kg)

2 EP: Energy productivity (oil) (MJ/ha/year)

3 e_f: equivalence factor of forests (gha/ha)

4 The whole footprint of the construction materials is allocated to CO₂ absorption land,
5 since the wooden construction materials represent a small percentage of the total.

6 The material consumption is determined through the RQDB. The embodied energy
7 values were obtained from various sources (Solís-Guzmán, 2011), by taking the
8 average of the values available as the energy value. This embodied energy includes
9 the manufacture and transportation of construction materials.

10 **2.5. Determination of the machinery EF**

11 In order to determine the fuel consumption due to the machinery involved in the work,
12 the total hours of machinery used is calculated from the project bill of quantities and the
13 RQDB, and then the economic cost of the machinery fuel can be calculated, together
14 with its total consumption. In previous work (Solís-Guzmán, 2011), the whole machine
15 cost, which includes machine depreciation, maintenance, and fuel costs, was
16 considered as fuel cost, and was then transformed into energy consumed. In the
17 present work, a revised methodology is used after performing a machinery cost
18 analysis (Ramirez-de-Arellano, 2006), whereby it is established that only 20 % of the
19 total machinery cost can be considered as fuel cost, which includes fuel and
20 maintenance cost but not equipment depreciation. The litres of fuel consumed are
21 determined using the current cost of fuel in Spain of 1.365€/l (CORES, 2013). The
22 machinery EF is determined following the procedure explained in the mobility section.

23

24

1 2.6. Determination of the electricity EF

2 The current electricity consumption is not available for the 92 projects analyzed.
3 Instead, the electricity consumed in the construction is determined by means of a
4 polynomial formula (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013).

5 In order to determine the electricity EF, it is necessary to identify the electricity mix in
6 Spain. The mix is formed of 15.0% coal, 5.2% oil, 29.4% gas, 19.8% nuclear, and the
7 remaining electricity is generated from renewable sources (Spain MI, 2012). The first
8 assumption is that renewable energies have very high energy productivity (EP)
9 (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996). The construction of wind parks and hydraulic plants
10 has minimal emission and their energy footprint is considered irrelevant as compared
11 to the energy footprint from fossil fuels and nuclear energy. For the other electric
12 energy sources, the EP of fuels is considered as per Table 6 and the efficiency factor
13 for electricity production is assumed to be 0.3 (IDAE, 2011). The absorption factor is
14 the same as in the mobility section. The electricity generation is not calculated from a
15 life-cycle perspective, and only direct emissions of electricity generation are taken into
16 account.

17 The formula used is:

$$18 \quad EF_{we} = \sum_i \frac{P_i}{EP_i} \cdot e_f \quad (6)$$

19 EF_{we} : Weighted ecological footprint of electricity consumption (gha/year)

20 P_i : Primary energy consumption of source i (GJ)

21 EP_i : Energy productivity of source i (GJ/ha/year)

22 e_f : equivalence factor of forests (gha/ha)

1 The consumption is calculated from the primary energy consumption i and the energy
2 productivity, applied to each of the sources.

3 **2.7. Determination of the EF of construction and demolition waste**

4 In this section, the environmental impact of construction and demolition waste (CDW) is
5 analyzed. Two types of waste are considered in accordance with the management
6 models of the CDW treatment plants in Spain: excavated earth, and mixed CDW.
7 Mixed CDW groups together the remains of materials generated during the execution
8 of the work units and the packaging of the materials. In new construction work,
9 excavated earth may represent over 80% of CDW, while the mixed CDW is distributed
10 among the remains of materials and its packaging (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2009).

11 The conversion rate is calculated by using the formula (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013),

$$12 \quad CR_x = \frac{EI_x}{EP} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\%R_x}{100} \cdot \frac{\%SE_x}{100}\right) \cdot e_f \quad (7),$$

13 where each of these terms is:

14 CR_x : Weighted Conversion Rate of CDW (gha/year/t)

15 EI_x : Energy Intensity of the production of the material from which the waste is made.

16 For these values, the energy intensities of the materials to be recycled must be known.

17 The data is summarized in Table 8.

18 EP : Energy Productivity of the waste (assumed to be equal to that of fossil fuels).

19 $\%R_x$: Recycling rate of waste x . The excavated earth is 100% reused on site. The
20 mixed CDW has a recycling rate of 70%.

21 $\%SE_x$: percentage of energy saved by recycling (Table 8).

1 Finally, the same expression as employed for the determination of the MSW EF,
2 equation 4, is used.

3 **2.8. Determination of the EF of water consumption**

4 Although the footprint of water consumption is not reflected in EF methodology, this
5 contribution is included in the present analysis. The current data of water consumed by
6 the 92 projects remains unavailable, but water consumption data from Seville's water
7 supply company from another ninety projects has been analyzed, the corresponding
8 average water consumption per project type determined, and the results are
9 summarized in Table 9 (Trigo-Ledesma, 2013).

10 In order to determine the EF, the forest is considered as a water producer, whereby the
11 consumption of this resource is included in that of forest land. In order to calculate
12 forest productivity (m³/ha/year), it is assumed that a forest of wetlands can produce
13 1,500 m³ of fresh water per hectare per year (Domenech Quesada, 2007). Therefore,
14 the formula employed for the calculation of the EF of water consumption is:

$$15 \quad EF_{ww} = \frac{W}{FP} \cdot e_f \quad (8),$$

16 EF_{ww}: Weighted ecological footprint of water consumption (gha/year)

17 W: Water consumption (m³)

18 FP: Forest productivity (m³/ha/year)

19 e_f: equivalence factor of forests (gha/ha)

20 **2.9. Determination of the built land EF**

21 This footprint is obtained by calculating the area consumed by the urbanization and the
22 building under study, through the planning of each project analyzed. As defined by the
23 EF methodology, the allocated surface is in the form of "productive land used directly."

1 The EF calculation becomes,

2
$$EF_{wb} = S \cdot e_b \quad (9),$$

3 where:

4 EF_{wb} : Weighted EF of built land (gha/year)

5 S: Surface area consumed (ha/year)

6 e_b : Equivalence factor of built land

7 The land used directly is considered to have the productivity of agricultural land, since
8 most of the infrastructure and built environment are located in areas of agricultural
9 quality.

10

11 **3. Results**

12 **3.1. Project budget and resource data-base**

13 The manpower on the construction site generates a significant EF due to food, mobility
14 and MSW generated. Once the total number of manpower hours for the entire project is
15 calculated, which is obtained from the RQDB, the EF_m from the different foods that
16 make up the daily meals of the workers are then obtained. Following the guidelines
17 raised in Section 2.2, a mobility EF is obtained. Moreover, the MSW generated by the
18 workers is calculated. Food, mobility and MSW EF are shown in Table 10, according to
19 the number of floors. The manpower-related EF represents about one third of the total
20 EF in all projects (Figure 2).

21 In Table 10, the waste EF is divided into CDW (70% approx.) and MSW (30% approx.).

22 In Figure 2, CDW and MSW represent 3% of the total EF and the food EF includes
23 pastures, productive sea, cropland and food preparation energy and represents almost

1 all the manpower EF; the mobility EF is less than 1% and is therefore not represented
2 in the figure.

3 The EF of construction materials used in the project is also determined from the
4 quantities and the RQDB, and the Total Embodied Energy is calculated in the process
5 of building construction using the methodology proposed, resulting in the energy (fossil)
6 EF, Table 10. The materials represent 44% (Figure 2) of the total EF which together
7 with the manpower EF control almost 80% of the EF of dwelling construction.

8 Furthermore, in Figure 3, the percentages of the material EF for the most
9 representative materials are shown, according to the number of floors. Concrete, steel,
10 ceramic, polystyrene and PVC materials represent 80% of the total material EF,
11 independent of the building type. This implies that 35% of the total EF is controlled by
12 these five construction materials.

13 The third resource consumed, which is determined from the project budget and the
14 RQDB, is the machinery fuel consumption whose results appear in Table 10. In this
15 case, the impact of combustion engine machinery on the construction site is very low,
16 since this type of machinery is mainly used in the first stages of the work (earthworks
17 and foundation), while in the following construction stages, electric machinery, such a
18 tower cranes, is used, which runs on electricity and has high consumption.

19 The RQDB created in the present analysis allows the calculation of 80% of the total
20 footprint. The remaining impacts are described in the following section.

21 **3.2. General project characteristics**

22 The EF of electricity, CDW and built land are determined from the general project
23 characteristics. First, the electric energy EF is obtained from the polynomial formula
24 (Solís-Guzmán et al., 2013), which determines the percentage of overall costs that
25 correspond to the energy consumption. Since the energy consumption of machinery is

1 already calculated, the difference between total energy consumption and fuel
2 consumption is therefore the electricity consumption.

3 The electricity consumption in kWh is obtained from the billing model used by the
4 power supplier. In order to obtain the electricity footprint, it is necessary to determine
5 the source of electricity in Spain (Spain MI, 2012). As explained above, only the
6 footprint from fossil fuels and nuclear energy is considered. The results appear in
7 Table 10. The electricity EF represents 18% of the total EF (Figure 2).

8 The generation of CDW is determined by means of a software tool (Solís-Guzmán et
9 al., 2009) and the waste conversion rates are calculated using the methodology
10 proposed. The results are shown in Table 10. This EF represents about 2% of the total
11 in all projects analyzed.

12 For the built land EF, the total area consumed must be indicated. To this end, the
13 surface area for blocks and surface area for roads are computed. By means of an
14 equivalence factor of 2.21 gha/ ha, the resulting EF of built land is calculated in
15 gha/year (Table 10). This is less than 1% of the total. The same happens with the
16 water consumption during the construction work which results in a forest footprint,
17 whereby the EF represents less than 1 % (Table 10).

18 In Figure 4, the energy EF is formed of several factors: materials, electricity, energy
19 consumed for food production, and waste. The main generators are materials and
20 electricity, but it is also an interesting result that food energy is also significant in the
21 building construction EF.

22 Finally, EF per capita is calculated in Table 10, based on the number of people per
23 dwelling (Spain MH, 2006) and the number of bedrooms per dwelling as obtained from
24 the Ministry of Development in Spain (2011). One-and two-floor detached houses
25 generate an EF that is 1.6 and 1.26 times higher than multi-family buildings,

1 respectively. One-floor detached houses also imply 2.6 times higher EF per person
2 since their occupation is lower than in multi-story buildings.

3 In general, three main aspects are identified that control the dwelling construction EF:
4 the manpower food intake, the embodied energy of the construction materials and the
5 electricity consumed on the construction site. On the other hand, water consumption
6 in-situ, workers mobility, combustion engine machinery and direct built land EF are
7 insignificant compared to the first three factors.

8

9 **4. Conclusions**

10 The EF of dwelling construction projects in Spain has been evaluated successfully.
11 The following can be concluded: the EF is sensitive to changes in building
12 characteristics, such as whether the dwelling is detached, is of one or two floors, and is
13 a multi-family dwelling, and these changes significantly affect the results.

14 The EF evaluation in the dwelling construction sector has made it necessary to define a
15 database of resources per construction system. This has been carried out for the most
16 common building characteristics in Spain, where the Andalusia Construction Cost
17 Database, classification system and quantification model, has been used as reference.
18 The resources have been easily divided into three categories: materials, manpower,
19 and machinery.

20 A methodology and structure has been defined which can be adapted to other
21 countries by means of local construction breakdown systems, by following the
22 proposed steps: define the budget quantities into construction systems; then transform
23 these into impacts such as materials, manpower and machinery; and finally, determine
24 the resources consumed and their corresponding EF. The new model improvements
25 have been centred on the calculation of the energy embodied in the construction
26 material, and the EF calculation of water and machinery, as explained in the
27 introduction.

28 The evaluation of the manpower and the construction materials yields significant
29 impact on the total EF, as observed when various scenarios are analyzed, such as
30 those involving detached houses and multi-family buildings, and when their

1 consumption is defined with respect to other activities that take place on the
2 construction site.

3 The results show that the most important factors in the EF calculation are: construction
4 materials (44%), manpower (35%) and on-site electricity consumption (18%). The least
5 significant are: mobility, machinery, water and direct land consumption. As part of the
6 energy EF the construction materials and electricity are the most prominent.

7 Five construction materials control 35% of the total EF, these being: concrete, steel,
8 ceramics, polystyrene and PVC. Strategies in order to reduce dwelling construction EF
9 can focus on using recycled concrete and steel, reused ceramics and insulation with
10 low embodied energy.

11 Another factor which can be significantly reduced is the electricity consumption on the
12 construction site by means of integrating renewable energy for domestic hot water and
13 using presence sensors to regulate lighting.

14 The relevance of this proposal for the scientific community and practitioners lies in the
15 possible application of the methodology, developed for the evaluation of various
16 construction projects, as an adaptable calculation tool for cost evaluation and control.
17 This tool can be adapted to any construction-work breakdown system commonly used
18 in the sector.

19 **Limitations and further research:**

20 In future work, the model sensitivity can be improved by means of identifying a greater
21 variety of construction systems for the foundation, the structure and the building
22 envelope. Another important step involves relating the energy consumption (electricity
23 and fuel) to the machinery classification of the resource data-base created. In this way,
24 quantification of the energy consumption can be directly generated based on the
25 machine power, efficiency and working hours.

26 Several project characteristics, such as renewable energy, sewage treatment
27 installations, and domestic solid waste installations, remain excluded from the analysis
28 and will become part of future research in order to render the present model more
29 robust.

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2 en el sector residencial en España.

3

4 **References:**

5

6 Acosta, G., González, J., Calvo, M., Sancho, F., 2001. Estimación de la Huella
7 Ecológica en Andalucía (Estimation of the Ecological Footprint in Andalusia). Junta de
8 Andalucía, Spain. <http://hdl.handle.net/10326/974> (accessed 15.07.11).

9 Andalusia Construction Cost Database (ACCD), 2010. (Base de Costes de la
10 Construcción de Andalucía, 2008. Consejería de Obras Pública y Vivienda de la Junta
11 de Andalucía.

12 [http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/obraspublicasyvivienda/portalweb/web/areas/vivienda/t
13 exto/bcfbb3af-ee3a-11df-b3d3-21796ae5a548](http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/obraspublicasyvivienda/portalweb/web/areas/vivienda/t
13 exto/bcfbb3af-ee3a-11df-b3d3-21796ae5a548).(accessed 01.11.13).

14 Bastianoni, S., Galli, A., Pulselli, R.M., Niccolucci, V., 2007. Environmental and
15 Economic Evaluation of Natural Capital Appropriation through Building Construction:
16 Practical Case Study in the Italian Context. *Ambio* 36(7), 559-565.

17 Bin, G., Parker, P., 2012. Measuring buildings for sustainability: Comparing the initial
18 and retrofit ecological footprint of a century home – The REEP House. *Applied Energy*
19 93:24-32.

20 Cagiao, J., Gómez, B., Domenech, J.L., Gutiérrez Mainar, S., Gutiérrez Lanza, H.
21 2011. Calculation of the corporate carbon footprint of the cement industry by the
22 application of MC3 methodology. *Ecological Indicators* 11, 1526-1540.

23 Colegio de Arquitectos Técnicos de Barcelona (COAT Barcelona), 2010. Congreso
24 Internacional. Rehabilitación y Sostenibilidad (International Congress.Rehabilitation
25 and Sustainability). Barcelona, Spain. <http://www.rs2010.org> (accessed 01.11.13).

- 1 Corporación de Reservas Estratégicas de Productos Petrolíferos (CORES), 2013.
2 Informe estadístico anual. Año 2012 (Annual statistical report 2012).
3 http://www.cores.es/pdf/Informe_Estadistico_Anual_2012.pdf (accessed 01.12.13).
4 Domenech Quesada, J.L., 2007. Huella Ecológica y Desarrollo Sostenible (Ecological
5 Footprint and Sustainable Development). AENOR. Madrid, Spain.
6 González-Vallejo, P., 2013. Evaluación de la huella ecológica de la edificación en el
7 sector residencial en España (Assessment of ecological footprint of the residential
8 buildings in Spain). Master thesis. University of Seville. Seville, Spain.
9 Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía (IDAE), 2011. Guía Práctica de
10 la Energía: Consumo Eficiente y Responsable (Practical Energy Guide: Efficient and
11 Responsible Consumption). IDAE. Madrid, Spain.
12 [http://www.idae.es/index.php/mod.pags/mem.detalle/recategoria.1161/id.542/reلمenu.](http://www.idae.es/index.php/mod.pags/mem.detalle/recategoria.1161/id.542/reلمenu.64)
13 64. (accessed 01.11.13).
14 Li, B., Cheng, DJ., 2010. Hotel ecological footprint model: Its construction and
15 application. Chinese Journal of Ecology 29(7):1463-1468.
16 Li, D., Li, Q., Du, H., 2008. Ecological footprint model of real estate development and
17 its case analysis. Dongnan Daxue Xuebao (Ziran Kexue Ban)/Journal of Southeast
18 University (Natural Science Edition) 38(4):732-735.
19 Malmqvist, T., Glaumann, M., 2009. Environmental efficiency in residential buildings – A
20 simplified communication approach. Build Environ 44, 937–947.
21 Marrero, M., Ramirez-de-Arellano, A., 2010. The building cost system in Andalusia:
22 application to construction and demolition waste management. Construction
23 Management and Economics, 28, 495–507.

- 1 Marrero, M., Fonseca, A., Falcon, R., Ramirez-de-Arellano, A., 2014. Schedule and
2 Cost Control in Dwelling Construction Using Control Charts, The Open Construction
3 and Building Technology Journal, 8, 63-79.
- 4 Meillaud, F., Gay, J., Brown, M.T.,2005. Evaluation of a building using the emergy
5 method. Sol Energy 79(2) ,204-212.
- 6 Olgay, V., 2008. Greenfoot: A tool for estimating the carbon and ecological footprint of
7 buildings. American Solar Energy Society - SOLAR 2008, Including Proc. of 37th ASES
8 Annual Conf., 33rd National Passive Solar Conf., 3rd Renewable Energy Policy and
9 Marketing Conf.: Catch the Clean Energy Wave 8:5058-5062.
- 10 Ramírez-de-Arellano-Agudo, A., 2006. Presupuestación de Obras. 3ª Edición (Giving a
11 Construction Estimate), Third ed. Secretariado de Publicaciones de la Universidad de
12 Sevilla. Seville, Spain.
- 13 Samadpour, P., Faryadi, S., 2008. Determination of ecological footprints of dense and
14 high-rise districts, case study of Elahie neighbourhood, Tehran. Journal of
15 Environmental Studies 34(45):63-72.
- 16 Sinivuori, P., Saari, A., 2006. MIPS analysis of natural resource consumption in two
17 university buildings. Build Environ 41(5), 657-668.
- 18 Solís-Guzmán, J., Marrero, M., Montes-Delgado, M.V., Ramírez-de-Arellano, A., 2009.
19 A Spanish Model for Quantification and Management of Construction Waste. Waste
20 Management 29 (9) 2542-2548.
- 21 Solís-Guzmán, J., 2011. Evaluación de la huella ecológica del sector edificación (uso
22 residencial) en la comunidad andaluza. (Assessing the ecological footprint of the
23 building sector (residential use) in Andalusia), Ph. D. thesis, Universidad de Sevilla,
24 Seville, Spain. <http://fondosdigitales.us.es/tesis/tesis/2051/evaluacion-de-la-huella->

- 1 ecologica-del-sector-edificacion-uso-residencial-en-la-comunidad-andaluza/ (accessed
2 15.12.13)
- 3 Solís-Guzmán, J., Marrero, M., Ramírez-de-Arellano, A., 2013. Methodology for
4 determining the ecological footprint of the construction of residential buildings in
5 Andalusia (Spain). *Ecol Ind* 25, 239-249.
- 6 Solís-Guzmán, J., Martínez-Rocamora, A., Marrero, M., 2014. Methodology for
7 determining the carbon footprint of the construction of residential buildings. In:
8 S.S.Muthu (Ed), *Assessment of Carbon Footprint in Different Industrial Sectors*,
9 Volume 1. Springer Science + Business Media, Singapore, pp.49-83.
- 10 Spain MD (Ministry of Development), 2011. *Construcción de edificios 2006-2010*
11 (construction of buildings 2006-2010). Madrid, Spain.
12 http://www.fomento.gob.es/MFOM/LANG_CASTELLANO/ESTADISTICAS_Y_PUBLICACIONES/(accessed 01.12.13)
- 14 Spain MH (Ministry of Housing), 2006. *Código Técnico de la Edificación (Building*
15 *Technical Code)*. Madrid, Spain. <http://www.codigotecnico.org/web/> (accessed
16 01.12.13)
- 17 Spain MI (Ministry of Industry), 2012. *Estructura de generación eléctrica en España. La*
18 *Energía en España 2012 (Structure of generation of electricity in Spain. Energy in*
19 *Spain 2012)*. [http://www.minetur.gob.es/energia/es-](http://www.minetur.gob.es/energia/es-ES/Documents/Energia_Espana_2011_WEB.pdf)
20 [ES/Documents/Energia_Espana_2011_WEB.pdf](http://www.minetur.gob.es/energia/es-ES/Documents/Energia_Espana_2011_WEB.pdf) (accessed 01.12.13)
- 21 Teng,J., Wu, X., 2014. Eco-footprint-based life-cycle eco-efficiency assessment of
22 building projects. *Ecological Indicators* 39:160-168.
- 23 Trigo-Ledesma, R., 2013. *Evaluación del consumo de agua en obras de edificios*
24 *residenciales y su aplicación a la huella ecológica (Assessment of water consumption*
25 *in residential building works and its application to the ecological footprint)*. Master
26 Thesis, University of Seville. Seville, Spain.
- 27 Wackernagel, M., Rees,W., 1996. *Our Ecological Footprint: Reducing Human Impact*
28 *on the Earth*. New Society, Gabriola Island, British Columbia.

- 1 Weidema, B.P., Thrane, M., Christensen, P., Schmidt, J., Løkke, S., 2008. Carbon
2 footprint. *J Ind Ecol*, 12:3-6.
- 3 WWF (WWF International), Global Footprint Network, ZSL (Zoological Society of
4 London), 2008. *Living Planet Report 2008*. WWF, Gland, Switzerland. ISBN 978-2-
5 88085-292-4. <http://assets.panda.org/downloads/lpr2008.pdf> (accessed 10.08.11).
- 6 WWF (WWF International), Global Footprint Network, ZSL (Zoological Society of
7 London), 2010. *Living Planet Report 2010*. WWF, Gland, Switzerland. ISBN 978-2-
8 940443-08-6. <http://assets.panda.org/downloads/lpr2010.pdf> (accessed 10.08.11).
- 9 Zabalza Bribián, I., Valero Capilla, A., Aranda Usón, A., 2011. Life cycle assessment
10 of building materials: Comparative analysis of energy and environmental impacts and
11 evaluation of the eco-efficiency improvement potential. *Building and Environment* 46,
12 1133-1140.
- 13 Zhao, XY., Mao, XW., 2013. Comparison environmental impact of the peasant
14 household in han, zang and hui nationality region: Case of Zhangye, Gannan and
15 Linxia in Gansu Province. *Shengtai Xuebao/Acta Ecologica Sinica* 33(17):5397-5406.

16

Figure 1: Methodology flowchart (González-Vallejo, 2013)
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Figure 2. Main factors generating an EF in the projects analyzed
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Materials

Electricity

Food

Waste

Figure 3: Material EF for the most representative materials
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Figure 4: Main factors generating an Energy EF
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Year	New buildings					Old buildings		
	Residential				Non-residential	Total	Rehab.	Demolished
	Individual Dwellings	Collective residence		Total				
		Permanent	Temporary					
2006	208,016	306	309	208,631	21,413	230,044	35,856	2,848
2007	165,833	197	292	166,322	20,825	187,147	33,359	26,141
2008	79,467	126	159	79,752	13,926	93,678	34,807	14,573
2009	39,349	102	113	39,564	12,180	51,744	33,267	7,984
2010	34,317	183	610	35,110	9,671	44,781	31,910	8,084
TOTAL	526,982	914	1,483	529,379	78,015	607,394	169,199	59,630

Table 1. Buildings constructed in Spain from 2006 to 2010

10AA	m2. Tiling	Cement mortar	0.51	0.44	0.34	0.37	0.39	0.43
10CE	m2. Plaster		1.70	1.81	1.45	1.50	1.57	1.66
10CG	m2. Whitewash	Plaster	3.35	2.93	2.15	2.37	2.43	2.70
10S	m2. Floors	Ceramic	0.79	0.75	0.77	0.79	0.79	0.83
10SS	m2. Pavers		0.12	0.00	0.16	0.13	0.12	0.06
10T	m2. Ceiling	Metallic frame	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.08
10R	m. Finishing	Limestone	0.16	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.09
11	CARPENTRY							
11CL	m2. Aluminium carpentry		0.15	0.14	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.12
11M	m2. Wood carpentry		0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11MA	m2. Closets		0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11MP	m2. Wood doors		0.12	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.13
11B	m2. Bannisters	Steel	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.06
11P	m2. Blinds		0.07	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.07
11R	m2. Safety bars		0.08	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01
12	GLASS							
12A	m2. Glass		0.12	0.11	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.11
13	COATING							
13PE	m2. Exterior paint		1.67	1.59	1.17	1.21	1.23	1.35
13PI	m2. Interior paint		3.51	3.36	2.57	2.77	2.81	3.09

Table 2. The resources, Qi, per square metre constructed

Table 3_revised

05F		m2. Concrete slab					
Unit	Component	05FUA00018	05FUA00118	05FUS00018	05FUS00108	05FUS00118	Average
Material							
kg	Steel bars B500S	1.990	2.990	2.190	3.490	3.490	2.830
u	Concrete block	5.400	4.860	5.400	4.860	4.635	5.031
m3	Concrete HA-25/P/20/lia	0.105	0.115	0.110	0.120	0.120	0.114
m3	Pine wood panel	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
m	Pre-stressed beam	1.397	2.338	1.397	2.338	2.338	1.962
u	Small material	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Manpower							
h	First-class official ironwork	0.026	0.046	0.030	0.054	0.054	0.042
h	First official	0.630	0.053	0.107	0.120	0.121	0.206
h	Specialized labour	0.306	0.356	0.356	0.406	0.406	0.366
Machinery							
h	Vibrator	0.070	0.070	0.080	0.075	0.080	0.075

Table 3. Quantities in concrete slabs per ACCD

Productive land category	Equivalence factor(gha/ha)
Cropland	2.51
Pastures	0.46
Forest	1.26
Productive sea	0.37
Built land	2.51

Table 4: Equivalence factors (WWF, 2010)

Productive land category	EF/meal (gha/year/meal)
Cropland	0.0075
Pastures	0.0501
Productive sea	0.0155
Forest Absorption of CO ₂	0.0077

Table 5. EF of workers' meals: cropland, pastures, productive sea, and forest absorption

Energy sources	E (kg C/GJ)	EP (GJ/ha/year)
(Acosta et al., 2001)		
<i>Fossil fuels</i>		
Coal	26.00	55
Oil	20.00	71
Natural gas	15.30	93
<i>Nuclear</i>	20.00	71

Table 6. Emission factors (E) and energy productivity (EP) of various energy sources

	Organic	Paper	Plastic	Glass
CR _x (gha/year/t)	0.3088	1.1478	0.5590	0.2981
G _x (t/worker/year)	0.2520	0.1200	0.0630	0.0400

Table 7. Weighted conversion rates for municipal solid waste

	Earth	Mixed CDW
EI_x (GJ/t)	0.10	5
EP (GJ/ha/year)	71	71
$\%R_x$	100	70
$\%SE_x$	90	90

Table 8: Parameters for the calculation of the CDW conversion rates

No. of floors above ground level	Sample size	Average consumption (m ³ /year/m ²)
1	22	0.29
2	31	0.24
3	21	0.13
4	15	0.15
5	3	0.15
10	2	0.07

Table 9. Water consumption per dwelling type

Impact	EF (gha/year/m ²)					
	Number of floors above ground level					
	1	2	3	4	5	10
EF pastures	0.049	0.043	0.032	0.035	0.035	0.036
EF productive sea	0.033	0.029	0.022	0.024	0.024	0.025
EF cropland	0.018	0.016	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.013
EF energy	0.258	0.203	0.167	0.165	0.162	0.161
Food	0.015	0.013	0.012	0.011	0.011	0.011
Mobility	3.87E-06	3.36E-06	2.68E-06	2.75E-06	2.75E-06	2.84E-06
Materials	0.167	0.126	0.107	0.105	0.102	0.100
Machinery	2.85E-04	1.77E-04	3.45E-04	2.95E-04	2.65E-04	1.80E-04
Electricity	0.067	0.055	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.043
CDW	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
MSW	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
EF forest	1.47E-04	9.53E-05	4.78E-05	7.08E-05	2.51E-05	2.52E-05
Water	1.47E-04	9.53E-05	4.78E-05	7.08E-05	2.51E-05	2.52E-05
EF built land	2.21E-04	1.11E-04	7.03E-05	5.58E-05	4.42E-05	2.20E-05
Total EF	0.358	0.291	0.233	0.236	0.233	0.235
Dwelling area (m ²)	181	143	72	70	72	72
Bedrooms	5	5	3	3	3	3
People per dwelling	6	6	4	4	4	4
People per unit area (m ²)	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
EF per person (gha)	10.811	6.936	4.191	4.132	4.196	4.236

Table 10. EF of residential buildings by number of floors above ground level